

1 An integral approach to sludge handling in a WWTP operated for
2 EBPR aiming phosphorus recovery: simulation of alternatives,
3 LCA and LCC analyses.

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15

16 **ABSTRACT**

17 As phosphorus is a non-renewable resource mainly used to produce fertilizers and helps to
18 provide food all over the world, the proper management of its reserves is a global concern since
19 it is expected to become scarcer in the near future.

20 In this work we assessed two different sludge line configurations aiming for P extraction and
21 recovery before anaerobic digestion and compared them with the classical configuration. This
22 study has been performed by simulation with the model BNRM2 integrated in the software
23 package DESASS 7.1. Configuration 1 was based on the production of a PO₄-enriched stream
24 from sludge via elutriation in the primary thickeners, while Configuration 2 was based on the
25 WASSTRIP® process and its PO₄-enriched stream was mechanically obtained with dynamic

26 thickeners. In both alternatives recovery was enhanced by promoting poly-phosphate (poly-P)
27 extraction under anaerobic conditions, for which both configurations were fully evaluated in a
28 full-scale WWTP. Both were also optimized to maximize phosphorus extraction. Their costs
29 and life cycles were also analysed.

30 The novelty of this research lies in the lack of literature about the integral evaluation of pre-
31 anaerobic digestion P recovery from wastewaters. This study included a holistic approach and
32 an optimization study of both alternatives plus their economic and environmental aspects.

33 In Configuration 1, the $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ load in the recovery stream reached 43.1% of the total influent P
34 load and reduced uncontrolled P-precipitation in the sludge line up to 52.9%. In Configuration
35 2, extraction was 48.2% of the influent P load and it reduced precipitation by up to 60.0%.
36 Despite Configuration 1's lower phosphorus recovery efficiency, it had a 23.0% lower life cycle
37 cost and a 14.2% lower global warming impact per hm^3 of treated influent than Configuration 2.
38 Configuration 1 also reduced the TAEC by 17.6% and global warming impact by 2.0% less than
39 Configuration 0.

40

41 1. INTRODUCTION

42 In nature, phosphorus (P) is directly linked to life and biological activity as it provides energy to
43 cells and is present in genetic material, bones and other structures (Smit et al., 2009, Van Dijk et
44 al., 2016). P causes pollution in aquatic ecosystems after excessive use of P-fertilizers and the
45 discharge of untreated wastewaters, inducing algal blooms, reducing the dissolved oxygen in the
46 water column and triggering the formation of P-deposits in sediments (Kroiss et al., 2011).
47 These issues are avoided by proper crop management and removing P in wastewater treatment
48 plants (WWTPs). P is currently removed in WWTPs biologically (enhanced biological
49 phosphorus removal, EBPR), chemically or a combination of both methods (Cornel and
50 Schaum, 2009). The combination of EBPR in the water line and anaerobic digestion in the
51 sludge line is a triggering factor for the uncontrolled precipitation of P-compounds inside and

52 downstream digesters, causing pipe blockages and deposits on the walls of pipelines, reactors
53 and other equipment (Martí et al., 2017).

54 The main use of P is in the food supply, as more than 80% of the mined product is used in the
55 food industry. An increase in its demand is expected in the near future as living standards and
56 the global population increase, but also the depletion of its reserves (Ciéslik and Konieczka,
57 2017; Robles et al., 2020). P and phosphate rock are thus included in the list of Critical Raw
58 Materials (EC, 2017). Around 90% of the highest quality reserves occur in Western Sahara and
59 Morocco, China, South Africa, Jordan and the USA, which adds extra complexity to its future
60 supply of food, as the resource has geopolitical interests and is subject to market fluctuations.
61 (Guedes et al., 2014).

62 Several initiatives are now under way in an attempt to alleviate its scarcity, including reuse and
63 recovery within its cycle. Egle et al. (2016) considered that implementing recovery techniques
64 in WWTPs could reduce Central Europe's dependence on external P-supplies by up to a 40%.
65 These techniques contribute to the evolution from the WWTP to the wastewater resource
66 recovery facility concept, in which wastewater is not considered as a mixture of pollutants
67 whose discharge into surface waters has to be avoided, but a rich source of valuable products.

68 P forms organic or inorganic compounds in WWTPs, the organic fraction being up to 60% of
69 total P in the sludge (Le Corre et al., 2009). Its mineralization requires long retention times and
70 takes place quantitatively in anaerobic sludge digestion. Inorganic P appears as i)
71 orthophosphate PO_4 , which is easily separated and afterwards assimilated by plants, and ii)
72 polyphosphate (poly-P), the solid compound that some organisms (poly-P accumulating
73 organisms, PAO) store after PO_4 uptake.

74 The main P-recovery product is struvite ($\text{NH}_4\text{MgPO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, MAP), which is considered a slow-
75 release fertilizer with low solubility and high P content (13% by mass). MAP crystallizes at a
76 pH of 7.5 when the molar ratio $\text{Mg}:\text{NH}_4:\text{PO}_4$ is around 1.3:4:1 (Shih et al., 2017; Peng et al.,

77 2018). Other recovered products as calcium phosphates have lower fertilizing potential (Robles
78 et al., 2020).

79 Direct application of P-enriched sludge after stabilization involves a simple recovery technique,
80 however it is forbidden in many countries due to the likely presence of heavy metals, persistent
81 organic pollutants and pathogens (Harrison *et al.*, 2006). This, together with the emergence of
82 P-recovery awareness, has triggered the research, development and full-scale implementation of
83 a wide variety of P-recovery techniques from different streams after anaerobic digestion: from
84 sludge (such as Airprex®, Nuresys and Elophos®) or centrifuge centrate (such as Naskeo®,
85 Ostara Pearl®, PHOSPAQ® or STRUVIA™). Under acidic conditions more P can be
86 recovered, as a part of the organic matter is mineralized and the precipitated compounds re-
87 dissolve after anaerobic digestion (Seaborne and Stuttgart processes). Nevertheless, the potential
88 of these processes is limited as they cannot avoid the uncontrolled precipitation of the
89 previously indicated P-compounds (Egle *et al.*, 2016). Other configurations, such as that
90 described in Pastor et al. (2008), Martí et al. (2017) or the WASSTRIP® process (Cullen et al.,
91 2013) aim to overcome this limitation by recovering P before anaerobic digestion.

92 Life cycle assessment (LCA) can quantify and compare the environmental impacts related to the
93 process per functional unit (ISO, 2006) and makes possible its comparison. Its use has been
94 promoted by the United Nations Environmental Program, however, it is rarely employed by
95 decision-makers, despite its high potential (Guérin-Schneider et al., 2018). Post-digestion
96 processes have already been compared by different approaches and methods in a number of
97 studies (Rodriguez-Garcia et al., 2014; Bradford-Hartke et al., 2015; Remy and Jossa, 2015;
98 Sena and Hicks, 2018), however, none have compared pre-digestion P-recovery technologies.
99 Also, few studies have been carried out on the life cycle costing (LCC) of P-recovery and these
100 only deal with costs for post-digestion technologies. The existing literature is based on assessing
101 the costs related to infrastructure, energy, chemicals, personnel, maintenance, products, by-
102 products and waste (Egle et al., 2016; Nättorp et al., 2017).

103 The novelty of this paper lies in its holistic assessment of technical, economic and
104 environmental aspects of three different P recovery strategies from sludge: one after anaerobic
105 digestion and two before anaerobic digestion. For this purpose, it is necessary to calibrate the
106 model of the WWTP in order to obtain reliable results of the different P recovery strategies
107 required for the LCA and LCC analysis. The post-anaerobic digestion strategy is based on
108 classical P recovery from the concentrates produced during the dewatering process, while the pre-
109 anaerobic digestion strategies are based on enhancing P extraction and separation by means of a
110 novel elutriation process and a process based on the WASSTRIP®.

111 2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

112 Both sludge line configurations assessed had the same goal: to increase P recovery and reduce
113 uncontrolled P-precipitation during anaerobic digestion. This can be achieved by enhancing
114 poly-P release from sludge and separating it before anaerobic digestion. The first configuration
115 (C1) evaluated the potential to recover P by mixing both thickened sludges under anaerobic
116 conditions in a mixing chamber and pumping the mixed sludge to the primary thickener to
117 obtain a liquid PO_4 -enriched stream to subsequently crystallize MAP (Figure 1, left). The
118 second configuration (C2) was based on the WASSTRIP process: the fermented primary sludge
119 was separated in the primary thickeners to obtain a VFA-enriched liquid stream which was
120 added to the waste-activated sludge (WAS) in a release tank. A PO_4 -enriched stream can then be
121 mechanically separated from sludge and finally recovered by crystallizing MAP (Figure 1,
122 right). In both configurations, VFA uptake and PO_4 release by PAO took place under the
123 anaerobic conditions in the mixing chamber (C1) and release tank (C2).

124 For comparison purposes, both configurations were assessed technically, economically and
125 environmentally, in the Murcia-Este WWTP (Spain). The first step was the calibration of the
126 Biological Nutrients Removal Model No.2 (Barat et al., 2013), BNRM2, with information from
127 three complete analytical campaigns to characterize the whole WWTP performance. The
128 different sludge line management strategies were then simulated on DESSAS 7.1 software

129 (Ferrer et al., 2008) to establish the optimal operating conditions and finally were
130 environmentally and economically evaluated.

131 2.1. Current Murcia Este WWTP configuration

132 The Murcia-Este WWTP mainstream consists of primary settling, an A2O biological reactor
133 with a total volume of 41,405 m³ (3.9% of the volume is anaerobic, 23.3% anoxic and 72.8%
134 aerobic) and secondary settling. The sludge line configuration is made up of two primary
135 gravity thickeners and two dissolved air flotation thickeners (DAF) for waste-activated sludge
136 (WAS). However, only one DAF thickener is currently being used. The thickened WAS is
137 electromagnetically hydrolysed and mixed with the primary sludge in a 79.2 m³ chamber and
138 then digested and dewatered to a final concentration of 20-25% of TSS. Figure 2, shows the
139 layout of the Murcia-Este WWTP with the different streams characterized for model calibration.

140 2.2. Layout of the sludge line configurations evaluated

141 The determining factor for the implementation of both configurations was extracting as much
142 poly-P as possible with the minimum investment cost by using as many elements of the current
143 WWTP layout as possible.

144 C1 was based on the elutriation of mixed sludge in the primary thickeners and increasing the
145 mixing chamber volume from 79 m³ to 609 m³ (Figure 3) with one of the secondary thickeners.
146 In this alternative the following effects were tested: 1) different elutriation flows (Q_{elut}) (from 0
147 to 1,000 m³ d⁻¹); 2) reduced primary sludge flows (from the current Q_{ps} of 5,685 m³ d⁻¹ to 1,500
148 m³ d⁻¹); 3) reduced sludge digestion flow (Q_{dig}) (from the current operation flow, 787 m³ d⁻¹ to
149 500 m³ d⁻¹).

150 C2 was based on the WASSTRIP configuration (Figure 4). In C2 the primary sludge was
151 fermented in the primary thickeners and the VFA concentration in the overflow stream was
152 increased by elutriation of the thickened sludge in the primary thickeners. The VFA-enriched
153 primary thickener overflow was mixed with the WAS in the secondary thickeners, which were
154 converted into anaerobic P-release tanks ($V_{\text{tot}} = 1,060 \text{ m}^3$). The next step was the separation of

155 an enriched $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ stream with a dynamic thickener. The effect of increasing Q_{elut} from 0 to
156 $1,000 \text{ m}^3\text{d}^{-1}$ while reducing Q_{ps} , from 5,685 to $1,500 \text{ m}^3\text{d}^{-1}$ were tested in this configuration.

157 2.3. Analytical method

158 Total and volatile suspended solids (TSS, VSS), total and soluble chemical oxygen demand
159 (COD_{tot} , COD_{sol}), total and soluble biological demand (BOD_{tot} , BOD_{sol}), total and soluble
160 phosphorus (P_{tot} , P_{sol}), total and soluble nitrogen (N_{tot} , N_{sol}), orthophosphate (PO_4), ammonium
161 (NH_4), nitrate (NO_3), and soluble metals (Mg_{sol} , Ca_{sol} , K_{sol}) analyses were carried out following
162 Standard Methods (APHA, 2005). Alkalinity and VFA were analysed as described in
163 Moosbrugger et al. (1992).

164 2.4. Assessing precipitation

165 Sludge line precipitation was estimated following the method described in Martí et al. (2008) by
166 applying mass balances for volatile solids, orthophosphate, magnesium and potassium in the
167 mixing chamber, anaerobic digestion, secondary digester and centrifuge for the current
168 configuration, plus primary thickener for C1 and the P-release tanks and dynamic thickeners for
169 C2.

170 2.5. Calibration and simulations

171 The model calibration and all simulations were carried out on DESASS 7.1 software (Ferrer et
172 al., 2008), which runs the BNRM2 (Barat et al., 2013), which includes all the equations,
173 parameters and components to accurately reproduce the biological and chemical processes in a
174 WWTP.

175 For calibration purposes, three intensive analytical campaigns were carried out at different
176 points of the water and sludge lines under normal operating conditions. These included an
177 exhaustive characterization of different parameters (see Section 2.3) in the streams indicated in
178 Figure 2. A total of 15 samples were analysed in each campaign (with between 16 and 18
179 parameters in each sample). All the samples were composite for 24 h (continuous sampling in
180 the water line and manual composite samples in the sludge line).

181 The model was calibrated by tuning the different parameters to minimize the differences
182 between the analytical results of three analytical campaigns and their respective simulations,
183 after which it was used to simulate the configurations above-mentioned.

184 2.6. Life cycle cost

185 The life cycle cost was assessed for each configuration calculating the annual cost, considering
186 the sludge line differential elements. It was considered the OPEX cost associated to: chemicals,
187 sludge disposal and energy consumption for operation and maintenance of thickening, digestion
188 (including the maintenance cost associated to the uncontrolled precipitation), dewatering and
189 combined heating and power (CHP). The CAPEX considered for C1 and C2 were: valves,
190 pumps, variable-frequency drives, stirrers, flow indicators and sludge blanket height controller
191 indicators and transducers, pipelines, PO₄ analysers and dynamic thickeners (see Tables 1 and
192 2). CAPEX were calculated at a 10% annual discount rate (*r*) and a project lifetime of 20 years
193 (*t*) according with Pretel et al. (2016). The cost analysis is given in Tables 3 and 4. Maintenance
194 included replacement of pumps, valves, stirrers, blowers, anti-scaling investment and other
195 differential elements. All the sludge was assumed to be used for agricultural applications.

196 Energy production was estimated at a methane calorific power of 38,000 kJ m⁻³ and 35%
197 efficiency (Seco et al., 2018). As the same personnel were assumed to run the infrastructure
198 after implementing both configurations, this item was excluded from the LCC calculation as it
199 was not a differential element. Maintenance costs were related to the replacement of equipment
200 after its lifetime, based on information retrieved from WWTP operators, equipment providers
201 and the cost of associated operations to reduce the effects of uncontrolled P precipitation. The
202 total annual equivalent cost (TAEC) was calculated as the sum of the annual capital expenses
203 (CAPEX) and operational requirements (OPEX), according to Eq.(1) (Ferrer et al. 2015):

$$TAEC = \frac{r(1+r)^t}{(1+r)^t - 1} \cdot CAPEX + OPEX \quad (1)$$

204 Return on investment (ROI) was calculated assuming a 95% MAP crystallization efficiency and
205 a market value of between €55 and €300 TmMAP⁻¹ (de Vries et al., 2017).

206 2.7. Life cycle assessment

207 The life cycle assessment (LCA) was performed according to UNE-EN ISO 14040 (ISO, 2006).
208 The inventory of materials and processes, which lists the volumes of inflows from the natural
209 environment and the outflows released into it, was compiled using the Ecoinvent Database v3
210 via SimaPro 8.5 (PRé Consultants; The Netherlands). The Hierarchist ReCiPe(H) v 1.02
211 midpoint method was employed to carry out the assessment of global warming (GW, quantified
212 as kgCO₂ eq.). The three scenarios were evaluated with functional units of 1 t of PO₄-P in the
213 recovery stream and a treated wastewater inflow of 1 hm³. Only the differential elements were
214 considered.

215 Different authors consider that the infrastructure's contribution to the LCA is negligible in
216 comparison to the operational impacts (Bradford-Hartke et al., 2015; Remy and Jossa, 2015;
217 Kjerstadius et al., 2017). In the present study, minimum modifications of the current sludge line
218 configuration (C0) were required to set up the C1 and C2 configurations. Neither configuration
219 required new reactors (existing elements were used, such as secondary thickeners not used in
220 the current sludge management configuration), only pumping, pipes and new dynamic
221 thickeners for C2 being necessary. For these reasons and due to the lack of reliable information,
222 the environmental impact related to the infrastructure were omitted, focusing on the operation of
223 the three P-recovery configurations.

224 3. RESULTS

225 3.1. Characterization

226 Table 5 shows the average values of the different parameters analysed during the three
227 analytical campaigns together with standard deviations. It is important to note the significant
228 fermentation in the primary thickener, which raised the VFA concentration from 95 mg COD/l
229 to 794 mgCOD/l. This fermentation is a key aspect of the study since the mix of VFA and
230 secondary sludge before the anaerobic digestion (in the mixing chamber in C1 and in the release
231 tank in C2, see Figure 1) triggered poly-P release. Also important is the increased ammonium
232 concentration during anaerobic digestion due to hydrolysis and the reduced phosphate

233 concentration, which confirmed the high level of phosphorus precipitation (see Section 3.4).
234 Different mass balances were applied for phosphate, magnesium and potassium in the mixing
235 chamber, anaerobic digestion, secondary digester and centrifuge, following Martí et al. (2008)
236 to quantify uncontrolled P precipitation. The analytical values determined the content of P, Mg
237 and K in organic matter, with values of $1.7 \text{ mgP} \cdot 100 \text{ mgVSS}^{-1}$, $0.5 \text{ mgMg} \cdot 100 \text{ mgVSS}^{-1}$, 1.1
238 $\text{mgK} \cdot 100 \text{ mgVSS}^{-1}$ (considering 32.7% of primary and 67.3% of secondary sludge).
239 Uncontrolled P precipitation in the sludge line was 577.9 kgP d^{-1} , anaerobic digestion being the
240 hot spot, as 95.7% of the precipitation took place there. Under the current WWTP configuration,
241 only 7.4% of the influent P load was present as $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ in the primary and secondary thickening
242 overflows and centrates from centrifuges (3.6% available only from centrates). This low P-
243 availability confirmed that the classical recovery of phosphorus from centrates drastically
244 reduces the potential recoverable P due to its precipitation.

245 3.2. Calibration

246 The BNRM2 model was calibrated to fit the simulated results with the three analytical
247 characterizations of the Murcia-Este WWTP under steady state conditions. As can be seen in
248 Figures S1-S4, the model was able to reproduce the biological and physical processes that took
249 place in the entire WWTP, which was fitted with the default values of the model parameters
250 proposed in BNRM2, with the exception of some parameters related to biological phosphorus
251 removal, hydrolysis and fermentation. The modified parameters are listed in Table 6.

252 The model simulations revealed significant differences in the behaviour of the bacteria
253 responsible for biological P removal (PAO) and organic matter hydrolysis and fermentation
254 (acidogenic bacteria) before and after the mixing chamber, probably due to electromagnetic
255 hydrolysis of the biological sludge before the mixing chamber (see Figure 2, between streams 7
256 and 7'), which probably reduced the bacteria's metabolism and performance. It is remarkable
257 the small volume of the anaerobic zone in the biological reactor (3.9% of the biological reactor),
258 which contrasts with the ability of the PAO bacteria developed in the reactor to reach high P
259 removal efficiencies (around 97%). For this reason, different parameters involved in the PAO

260 metabolism were modified, such as PHA accumulation rate (q_{PHA}) and volatile fatty acids half
261 saturation constants (K_A and K_{PRO}). Acidogenic activity (μ_{Acid}) was modified in order to
262 reproduce the high degree of fermentation observed at the bottom of the primary thickeners.
263 Hydrolytic activity (k_H) was changed in order to fit the experimentally measured soluble COD
264 balance in the gravity thickeners. This parameter was increased in the mixing chamber to
265 simulate the effect of the electromagnetic hydrolyser after secondary thickening.

266 3.3. Phosphorus extraction evaluation

267 3.3.1. Current configuration

268 The three analytical campaigns established the baseline of the current WWTP. Under the current
269 sludge line configuration (C0) the $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ concentration in the overflows of the primary and the
270 secondary thickener were 5.2 and 3.0 mg L^{-1} , which represents 3.8% of the influent P load. The
271 $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ concentration in the primary and secondary thickener overflows were 53.4 and 5.8 mg L^{-1}
272 respectively. 29.5% of the stored poly-P was released in the mixing chamber and $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$
273 concentration in the centrifuge centrate was 49.2 mg L^{-1} , 3.6% of the influent P, with a $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$
274 concentration of 921.1 mg L^{-1} . The sludge blanket height in the primary thickener was 0.80 m
275 and 8301 $\text{Nm}^3 \text{d}^{-1}$ of biogas was produced under the current configuration.

276 P recovered as MAP from the centrifuge centrate would give a production of 91.5 tMAP year^{-1} ,
277 assuming 95% crystallizer efficiency. It is important to note that the $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ concentration in this
278 recovery stream was 3.6% of the influent P load.

279 3.3.2. Alternative configurations C1 and C2

280 The proposed configurations (see Figures 3 and 4) were optimised by modifying different
281 operating conditions. Figures 5 and 6 show the simulation results in terms of potential P
282 recovery from the P-enriched streams and phosphate concentration under different operational
283 conditions. Figures S5 and S6 show the P mass balances in the optimized scenario for each
284 configuration.

285 As can be seen in Figure 5, reducing Q_{ps} from 5,685 to 1,500 $m^3 d^{-1}$ increased PO_4 concentration
286 in the recovery stream from 82.6 to 250.2 $mgP L^{-1}$. However, as shown Figure 6, the influent
287 extraction efficiency was reduced from 50.7% to 36.7%, while the sludge blanket height rose
288 from 0.65 to 1.15 m (data not shown).

289 According to the specifications of the crystallization process, it was necessary to achieve as high
290 a phosphate concentration as possible in the recovery stream and to keep it above 80 $mgP L^{-1}$.
291 As the operational limitations of the primary settlers in the Murcia-Este WWTP did not allow
292 reducing Q_{ps} below 2,500 $m^3 d^{-1}$ it was decided to fix Q_{ps} around 2,500 $m^3 d^{-1}$. In this condition,
293 the phosphate concentration was 169.1 $mgP L^{-1}$ with an extraction efficiency of 43.1%.

294 Raising Q_{elut} to 1,000 $m^3 d^{-1}$ increased PO_4 -P concentration in the recovery stream by about 3%.
295 The negligible effect of Q_{elut} on P extraction was due to the mixing chamber volume, and its
296 high hydraulic retention time (around 24 hours) promoted fermentation and extraction of the
297 PAO internal Poly-P, so that it was not necessary to mix primary and secondary sludge in the
298 mixing chamber. These results indicate that the optimal C1 operational conditions were $Q_{ps} =$
299 2,500 $m^3 d^{-1}$ with no elutriation flow. Considering a 95% efficiency of P recovery as MAP, the
300 annual production after crystallizing MAP would be 1,053.3 tMAP $year^{-1}$. The reduction of Q_{dig}
301 from the current value of 787 $m^3 d^{-1}$ to 500 $m^3 d^{-1}$ increased the extraction efficiency from
302 43.1% to 48.3%. However, this reduction of the sludge digestion flow was not considered, due
303 to a drastic rise in sludge blanket height up to 1.57 m, which compromised overall C1
304 performance due to the risk of the overflow of the primary thickeners.

305 Changing Q_{ps} and Q_{elut} in the C2 simulations showed that reducing Q_{ps} from 5,685 to 1,500 m^3
306 d^{-1} without elutriation did not significantly increase the PO_4 -P concentration in the recovery
307 stream (from 46.2 to 56.9 $mgP L^{-1}$). Raising Q_{elut} up to 1,000 $m^3 d^{-1}$ increased the concentration
308 in the recovery stream, reaching up to 104.2 $mgP L^{-1}$ for $Q_{ps} = 2,500 m^3 d^{-1}$ and 135.2 $mgP L^{-1}$
309 for 1,500 $m^3 d^{-1}$. The recovery efficiencies were 44.2%, 48.2 and 47.4% for Q_{ps} of 1,500 $m^3 d^{-1}$,
310 2,500 $m^3 d^{-1}$ and 5,685 $m^3 d^{-1}$, respectively. $Q_{ps} = 2,500 m^3 d^{-1}$ with $Q_{elut} = 1,000 m^3 d^{-1}$ was
311 considered the optimal operating conditions for this configuration (Figure 5 and Figure 6). The

312 annual MAP production increased by up to 1,176.8 t year⁻¹ with the same crystallization
313 efficiency as in C1.

314 Regarding anaerobic digestion performance, biogas production increased by around 1.5% in C1
315 and 7.4% in C2 due to the higher organic load in the anaerobic digesters due to the increase of
316 the COD load in the digesters (see Table 7).

317 3.4. Reduction of uncontrolled P precipitation

318 The implementation of both sludge line configurations significantly reduced uncontrolled
319 precipitation in relation to the current configuration (C0) of around 52.9% in C1 and 60.0% in
320 C2. The digesters remained as the main P sink in the sludge line with around 90% of total
321 precipitation. The available PO₄ in the overflows and centrates increased from 65.8 kgP d⁻¹
322 (7.4% of the influent P load) in the original configuration (C0) to 421.4 kgP d⁻¹ for C1 and
323 476.1 kgP d⁻¹ for C2 (Figure 7), considering all the overflows and centrates, which represent
324 47.4% and 53.6% of the influent P load respectively.

325 3.5. Life cycle costs

326 TAEC per ton of PO₄-P in the recovery stream and per hm³ of treated wastewater are shown in
327 Figures 8a and 8b respectively for each configuration. The cost was divided into OPEX and
328 CAPEX, considering 10% depreciation for 20 years considering the differential elements in the
329 sludge line and its operation between the three studied configurations. Regarding the results
330 normalized per ton of PO₄-P (Figure 8a), TAEC for C0 was 22,565 € and was reduced by 92.8%
331 in C1 and 91.7% in C2. These reductions were clearly due to the large amount of phosphorus
332 recovered in the alternatives focused on phosphorus extraction and recovery before anaerobic
333 digestion (C1 and C2) compared to the current configuration, which recovers phosphorus after
334 anaerobic digestion (C0).

335 However, normalizing the cost with a conventional functional unit, i.e. the influent flowrate of
336 treated wastewater (in hm³), the TAEC changed drastically, obtaining values of 7,696 € hm⁻³,
337 6,341 € hm⁻³ and 8,236 € hm⁻³ for C0, C1 and C2 respectively (Figure 8b). In this case C1 again

338 obtained the lowest TAEC (17.6% lower than C0) due to the significant reduction of
339 maintenance costs to mitigate uncontrolled P precipitation in the sludge line and higher biogas
340 production, despite the slight increase in the energy requirements (around 3.2% increase from
341 C0 to C1 mainly due to the thickening process and mixing chamber agitation). Despite the
342 greater reduction in maintenance costs and higher biogas production, C2 obtained the highest
343 TEAC due to higher energy and chemical consumption and the acquisition cost of new dynamic
344 thickeners.

345 CAPEX was 6.9% of TAEC for C1 and 13.2% for C2. This difference was mainly due to the
346 cost associated with the dynamic thickeners to obtain the PO₄-enriched stream (C2 required the
347 acquisition of 4 dynamic thickeners to treat 4,530 m³ d⁻¹ of sludge). C1 did not need any specific
348 equipment to obtain this PO₄-enriched stream. This configuration employed the existing primary
349 thickeners to separate the soluble PO₄-P in a specific stream.

350 Assuming 95% efficiency in the subsequent crystallization phase and a MAP market price
351 between 55 and 300 € tMAP⁻¹, the investment in the sludge line would be recovered in between
352 5 to 27 months for C1 and from 11 and 61 months for C2.

353 The results obtained in the LCC analysis confirmed that the sludge management configuration
354 based on the elutriation in the primary thickeners (C1) presented the lowest cost per ton of PO₄-
355 P in the recovery stream and per hm³ of treated wastewater.

356 3.6. Life cycle assessment

357 SimaPro 8.5 was used to compare the differential elements in operating the different
358 configurations. Figure 9a shows the global warming (GW) impact of the three approaches per t
359 of PO₄-P in the recovery stream. For C0, GW was the highest, 46,007 kg CO₂eq·tPO₄-P⁻¹. GW
360 for C1 and C2 was very similar, 3,917 kg CO₂eq·tPO₄-P⁻¹ and 4,088 kg CO₂eq·tPO₄-P⁻¹
361 respectively. Despite the higher P recovery in C2, the GW impact of this configuration is similar
362 to the one obtained in C1 due to its higher emissions associated to the increase in the energy and
363 chemicals consumption. However, using the influent flowrate of treated wastewater (hm³) as the

364 functional unit to normalize the impacts (Figure 9b), C2 emissions increased up to 14.2% over
365 C0, and its GW impact was 15,690 kg CO₂eq·hm⁻³, whilst for C1 it was reduced by up to 2.0%
366 (Figure 9b). Despite the fact that C1 produced less biogas, it required substantially less energy
367 for sludge pumping and thickening. The lower impact of C1 was mainly related to higher biogas
368 production. A similar behaviour between alternatives was observed in other impact categories,
369 such as, terrestrial acidification, freshwater eutrophication and mineral resource scarcity.
370 Further information on other environmental indicators can be found in Figures S7-S20 and
371 Table S1.

372 Same as in the cost analysis, the results obtained in the LCA confirmed that the sludge
373 management configuration based on the elutriation in the primary thickeners (C1) presented the
374 lowest impacts per ton of PO₄-P in the recovery stream and per hm³ of treated wastewater.

375 4. DISCUSSION

376 Currently, most studies on recovering phosphorus as struvite from wastewater focus on
377 crystallization of the centrates after the digestion process (Egle et al., 2016; Nättorp et al., 2017;
378 Sena and Hicks, 2018) and disregard the enormous amount of phosphorus that is lost due to
379 uncontrolled precipitation during and after anaerobic digestion. Only a few studies have
380 explored new sludge management strategies to minimize this phosphorus loss, for example
381 those based on phosphorus extraction and separation in a specific stream before the anaerobic
382 digesters (Lizarralde et al., 2019, Martí et al., 2017). These strategies have been evaluated in
383 different studies (Bouzas et al., 2019; Cullen et al., 2013) but have never been compared to a
384 real case study under technical, economic and environmental criteria. The present work tested
385 both configurations jointly with the classical system using the centrates from anaerobic
386 digesters.

387 Lizarralde et al. (2019) simulated different phosphorus management strategies in the Sur-
388 WWTP (Madrid, Spain), including, among others, a WASSTRIP-based process and achieved
389 23.8% of the influent phosphorus present as phosphate in the extraction stream. This is lower
390 than the one obtained in the present work (48.5%), mainly due to the lower efficiency of the

391 biological phosphorus removal in the water line (73% in the Sur-WWTP and 96% in the
392 Murcia-Este WWTP), which considerably reduced potential phosphorus recovery. However, the
393 results obtained in the present study are in agreement with those obtained by Gysin et al. (2018),
394 who found that the potential recovery of the WASSTRIP process was between 45% and 60% of
395 the influent P-load.

396 Bouzas et al. (2019) evaluated the overall performance of the Calahorra WWTP (Spain) after
397 the implementation of the new sludge management based on the phosphorus extraction by
398 elutriation in the primary thickeners (equivalent to the C1 in the present work) and found that
399 this sludge management system reduced uncontrolled precipitation by 43%, in agreement with
400 the present study (52.9%). However, there are significant discrepancies in the amount of
401 phosphate present in the extraction stream. Bouzas et al. (2019) obtained 19% of influent
402 phosphorus in the extraction stream as phosphate, while this was 43.1% in the present study.
403 These discrepancies could be attributed to the low capacity of the primary thickener of the
404 Calahorra-WWTP to admit more solids in the elutriation stream and the lower phosphorus
405 removal efficiency than in Murcia-Este WWTP (between 80-92% in the former and 96% in the
406 latter). However, further research is needed in a full-scale experiment to confirm the simulated
407 results of the present work.

408 5. CONCLUSIONS

409 This study confirms that the implementation of any of the proposed configurations to modify
410 sludge management before anaerobic digestion is economically viable and highly efficient in
411 comparison with the currently widespread post-digestion recovery technologies. Optimal C1
412 operation increased PO_4 concentration in the recovery stream by up to 169.1 mgP L^{-1} ,
413 corresponding to 43.1% of the influent P load, and reduced uncontrolled P-precipitation by 53%
414 in comparison to C0. On the other hand, the optimal operation of C2 was able to recover 48.2%
415 of the influent P load with a concentration of 104.2 mgP L^{-1} , reducing uncontrolled precipitation
416 by up to 60% in comparison to C0.

417 Despite its slightly lower recovery potential, C1 shows a significantly lower CAPEX and
418 OPEX, mainly because this configuration does not require the acquisition of dynamic thickeners
419 to obtain the PO₄-enriched stream from sludge and has lower sludge pumping flows and a
420 smaller environmental impact. The analysis of the implementation of both alternatives in the
421 Murcia-Este WWTP showed C1 has a lower TAEC, ROI and environmental footprint and is
422 therefore considered the most favourable sludge line configuration for P recovery.

423 These results show how performing complete holistic studies for each situation are essential to
424 differentiate between apparently similar options, can make substantial progress towards a new
425 paradigm and contribute to overcoming the limitations of the current technologies.

426 6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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429 7. REFERENCES

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Table 1[Click here to download Table: Table 1.docx](#)

Table 1. Acquisition costs for C1.

Element	n°	Total cost (€)	Source
Pneumatic guillotine valve DN 200	1	634.85	BEDEC, 2019 / Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Pneumatic guillotine valve DN 150	17	9,062.02	BEDEC, 2019 / Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Manual valves	2	674.30	BEDEC, 2019
Motorised guillotine valve DN 150	3	5,803.74	BEDEC, 2019 / Murcia-Este WWTP
VFD 7.5 kW	12	11,395.74	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Agitators	2	17,261.02	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Level indicator	1	1,146.66	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Sludge blanket flow indicator	2	8,500.00	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Flow indicator	7	11,030.11	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Pumping 1	3	6,830.25	Bombas Ideal S.A., 2018 / Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Pumping 2	3	6,830.25	Bombas Ideal S.A., 2018 / Murcia-Este WWTP operators
P analyzer	1	23,285.88	Endress+Hauser, 2018 / Murcia-Este WWTP operators
PLC adjustment	1	13,789.87	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
SCADA programming	1	7,123.20	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
SCADA+PLC programming	1	20,913.07	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Ditch digging	24	1,578.24	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Filling 1	8	148.48	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Filling 2	16	347.20	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Polyethylene pipes	287 (m)	6,483.33	Frans Bonhomme, 2019 / Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Total		131.925,14	

Table 2[Click here to download Table: Table 2.docx](#)

Table 2. Acquisition costs for C2

Element	n°	Total cost (€)	Source
Pneumatic guillotine valve DN 200	1	634.85	BEDEC, 2019 / Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Pneumatic guillotine valve DN 150	22	11,727.32	BEDEC, 2019 / Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Manual valves	2	674.30	BEDEC, 2019
Motorised guillotine valve DN 150	3	5,803.74	BEDEC, 2019 / Murcia-Este WWTP operators
VFD 7.5 kW	9	8,592.30	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
VFD removal	3	0.00	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Agitators	4	34,522.04	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Level indicator	2	2,293.32	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Sludge blanket flow indicator	2	8,500.00	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Flowindicator	3	4,727.19	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Pumping 1	3	12,201.33	Bombas Ideal S.A., 2018 / Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Pumping 2	3	6,830.25	Bombas Ideal S.A., 2018 / Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Dynamic thickeners	4	180,400.00	Alfa Laval Iberia, 2018
P analyzer	1	23,285.88	Endress+Hauser, 2018 / Murcia-Este WWTP operators
SCADA+PLC programming	1	20,913.07	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Ditch digging	24	1,578.24	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Filling 1	8	148.48	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Filling 2	16	347.20	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Polyethylene pipes	287 (m)	6,483.33	Murcia-Este WWTP operators
Total		329,662.84	

Table 3[Click here to download Table: Table 3.docx](#)

Table 3. Energy and polymer consumption for C0, C1 and C2.

	Energy consumption (kWh year⁻¹)		
	C0	C1	C2
Primary sludge pumping to primary thickeners	157,680	100,740	100,740
Thickened primary sludge pumping to mixing chamber	19,272	0	0
Thickened primary sludge pumping to digestion	0	47,304	0
Thickened primary sludge towards primary thickeners (elutriation) and mixing chamber	0	0	56,064
Thickened biological sludge pumping to mixing chamber	43,800	0	0
Thickened biological sludge pumping to primary thickeners	0	43,800	0
Biological sludge pumping to dynamic thickening	0	0	271,560
Secondary thickener recirculation pumping	297,840	297,840	0
Secondary thickener blower	19,272	19,272	0
Dynamic thickener	0	0	198,414
Mixing chamber stirring	6,938	6,938	6,938
P-release tanks stirring	0	46,428	92,856
Anaerobic digestion + sludge dewatering + CHP	1,523,047	1,523,047	1,523,047
	Polyelectrolyte consumption (t year⁻¹)		
	C0	C1	C2
Secondary thickeners	21.8	22.5	0.0
Dynamic thickeners	0.0	0.0	38.1

Table 4[Click here to download Table: Table 4.docx](#)

Table 4. OPEX costs.

		Cost	Reference
External energy cost	0.138	€ kWh ⁻¹	Pretel et al. (2016)
Co-generated energy cost	0.008	€ kWh ⁻¹	Wang et al. (2019)
Polyelectrolyte (polyacrylamide)	2.350	€ kg ⁻¹	Pretel et al. (2016)
Polyelectrolyte consumption (secondary thickeners)	3.0	kg tTSS ⁻¹	Murcia Este WWTP operators
Polyelectrolyte consumption (dynamic thickeners)	5.0	kg tTSS ⁻¹	Alfa Laval Iberia, 2018
Agricultural application of the sludge	4.8	€ tTSS ⁻¹	Pretel et al. (2016)
Uncontrolled P-precipitation mitigation	0.489	€ · t P-precipitated	Neetheling and Benisch (2004)

Table 5[Click here to download Table: Table 5.docx](#)

1 Table 5. Average characterization in the different sampling points (see Figure 2).

Sampling point	Flow rate (m ³ d ⁻¹)	TSS/TS* (mg L ⁻¹)	VSS/VS** (%)	COD _{tot} (mg L ⁻¹)	COD _{sol} (mg L ⁻¹)	VFA (mg L ⁻¹)	P _{tot} (mg L ⁻¹)	N _{tot} (mg L ⁻¹)	PO ₄ -P (mg L ⁻¹)	NH ₄ -N (mg L ⁻¹)	Ca _{sol} (mg L ⁻¹)	Mg _{sol} (mg L ⁻¹)	K _{sol} (mg L ⁻¹)	pH
0	97,701 ± 18,839	404 ± 65	79.7 ± 4.9	654 ± 102	194 ± 96	105 ± 20	9.1 ± 2.2	76.8 ± 7.0	4.9 ± 0.5	50.6 ± 1.8	132.5 ± 12.8	66.1 ± 4.2	37.5 ± 5.5	7.5 ± 0.1
1	92,983 ± 18,203	289 ± 66	80.9 ± 2.8	572 ± 114	196 ± 95	105 ± 49	7.8 ± 2.3	66.8 ± 9.5	4.5 ± 0.7	50 ± 2.7	130.3 ± 11.2	63.4 ± 5.8	34.6 ± 9.2	7.5 ± 0.1
2	157,301 ± 23,381	2,869 ± 601	79.0 ± 0.7	3,863 ± 644	n.a.	n.a.	86.8 ± 24.6	210 ± 43.8	0.1 ± 0.0	4.3 ± 3.5	142.1 ± 10.4	59.4	34.9 ± 0.9	7.2 ± 0.1
3	97,100 ± 18,723	10.3 ± 10.2	83.7 ± 2.7	38 ± 11	34 ± 57	n.a.	0.3 ± 0.0	16.3 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0	3.3 ± 1.7	134.2 ± 13.2	61.2 ± 5.5	32.8 ± 2.6	7.3 ± 0.1
4	4,718 ± 1,690	2,868 ± 902	73.9 ± 7.5	3,592 ± 971	223 ± 6	97 ± 15	37.5 ± 13.7	326.7 ± 40.1	5.4 ± 0.5	55.7 ± 4.6	142.4 ± 18.0	66.1 ± 8.1	32.9 ± 4.1	7.3 ± 0.1
5	2,232 ± 217	7,147 ± 1,151	78.7 ± 0.9	8,504 ± 1,129	33 ± 10	n.a.	201.0 ± 50.7	529.2 ± 142.7	2.7 ± 0.2	2.9 ± 2.2	136.0 ± 9.9	63.6 ± 3.6	34.9 ± 3.6	6.9 ± 0.0
6	220 ± 56	46,830 ± 14,090	75.2 ± 3.2	51,307 ± 10,715	1,049 ± 326	794 ± 194	312.1 ± 105.5	n.a.	26.6 ± 9.1	87.5 ± 4.2	182.6 ± 15.4	81.8 ± 11.8	52.1 ± 4.8	6.4 ± 0.1
7	567 ± 89	36,040 ± 2,995	79.1 ± 2.0	32,789 ± 2,822	119 ± 62	n.a.	736.1 ± 150.9	n.a.	91.8 ± 18.6	15.4 ± 4.1	140.7 ± 8.0	72.6 ± 3.0	96.9 ± 22.8	n.a.
7'	567 ± 89	33,906 ± 2,545	78.2 ± 1.5	32,906 ± 2,743	126 ± 51	n.a.	669.1 ± 59.9	n.a.	110.0 ± 26.9	19.3 ± 4.6	134.2 ± 17.1	78.1 ± 4.2	96.8 ± 8.7	n.a.
8	4,498 ± 1,742	529 ± 72	83.3 ± 3.7	823 ± 335	102 ± 39	n.a.	9.3 ± 1.4	n.a.	5.3 ± 0.8	40.7 ± 7.5	141.2 ± 15.1	69.8 ± 5.6	41.5 ± 11.9	7.5 ± 0.1
9	1,665 ± 139	130 ± 22	72.2 ± 3.0	125	29 ± 8	n.a.	5.3 ± 0.4	n.a.	3.8 ± 0.2	5.2 ± 3.2	142.7 ± 18.7	61.6 ± 7.5	26.1 ± 1.0	7.4 ± 0.1
10	787 ± 70	40,547 ± 3,614	77.0 ± 2.3	42,895 ± 9,546	674 ± 388	474 ± 324	536.9 ± 55.9	n.a.	136.0 ± 47.9	72.4 ± 32.1	127.7 ± 2.8	84.7 ± 8.3	94.8 ± 34.4	6.5 ± 0.1
11	787 ± 70	28,211 ± 1,352	63.7 ± 2.0	24,323 ± 1,578	788 ± 116	76 ± 12	505.1 ± 40.1	n.a.	73.1 ± 12.1	879.4 ± 56.7	89.2 ± 31.4	11.3 ± 16.2	372.0 ± 19.3	7.4 ± 0.0
12	787 ± 70	28,718 ± 1,122	64.0 ± 4.6	23,708 ± 2,117	1,700 ± 1,483	143 ± 8	544.6 ± 167.7	n.a.	55.8 ± 13.7	958.5 ± 191.8	71.4 ± 16.6	8.2 ± 10.5	389.5 ± 47.2	7.6 ± 0.6
13	668 ± 58	2,612 ± 1,580	74.2 ± 2.7	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	138.7 ± 15.6	n.a.	49.2 ± 8.4	921.1 ± 122.7	60.8 ± 23.1	2.9 ± 5.0	345.8 ± 16.2	8.1 ± 0.2

2

3 * TSS were determined in streams 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 13 and TS were determined in streams 6, 7, 7', 10, 11, 12

4 ** VSS were determined in streams 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 13 and VS were determined in streams 6, 7, 7', 10, 11, 12

Table 6[Click here to download Table: Table 6.docx](#)

Table 6. Fitted parameters for the biological model of the Murcia-Este WWTP.

	Bibliography	Water & Sludge Lines	Mixing Chamber
Phosphate-accumulating organisms			
q_{pha} (d^{-1})	3.00 (ASM2d)	9.00	1.55
K_A (mg COD L^{-1})	4.00 (ASM2d)	3.30	3.30
K_{PRO} (mg COD L^{-1})	4.00 (ASM2d)	3.30	3.30
Acidogenic bacteria			
μ_{Acid} (d^{-1})	1.28 (BNRM2)	8.00	8.00
k_H (d^{-1})	43.00 (BNRM2)	13.30	75.00

Table 7[Click here to download Table: Table 7.docx](#)

Table 7. Fitted parameters for the biological model of the Murcia-Este WWTP.

Configuration	Organic load anaerobic digestion (kP d ⁻¹)	Biogas production (Nm ³ d ⁻¹)
C0	30,577	8301
C1	31,498	8426
C2	32,292	8913

Figure 1

Figure 1. Principles for both assessed configurations. Configuration 1 (left) and Configuration 2 (right).

Figure 3

Figure 3. C1 scheme configuration in the Murcia-Este WWTP.

Figure 4

Figure 4. C2 scheme configuration in the Murcia-Este.

Figure 5

Figure 5. PO_4 concentration in the recovery stream for C1 (green) and C2 (blue) depending on Q_{ps} and Q_{elut} .

Figure 6

Figure 6. C1 (left) and C2 (right): percentage of the PO₄ load from the influent P in the recovery stream depending on Q_{ps} and Q_{elut} .

Figure 7

Figure 7. Precipitation of PO_4 in the sludge line (negative values) and available (positive values) in the liquid streams generated under the different configurations.

Figure 8

Figure 8. Total annual cost estimations for the different configurations (a) per ton of PO₄-P in the recovery stream and (b) per hm³ of treated wastewater.

Figure 9

Figure 9. Global warming impact of the three configurations (a) per ton of PO₄-P in the recovery stream and (b) per hm³ of treated wastewater.